

SUBJECT OF THE CRIME OF HUMAN TRAFFICKING

Kurbanov Davlat Ravshanovich

Head of the Department of "Special Legal Sciences" of the Faculty of Law
of Samarkand State University named after Sh.Rashidov

Doctor of philosophy, Associate Professor,

E-mail: davlatkurbonov73@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11519355>

Annotation: This article analyzes in detail the subject of this act. In particular, the signs of a general subject and a special subject of a crime in the field of human trafficking are considered, the legal norms of domestic and foreign countries, the opinions of scientists and an analysis of law enforcement practice in this regard are described and relevant proposals are put forward.

Keywords: human trafficking, criminal subject, natural person, sane, trafficker.

According to the theory of criminal law, the subject of the crime and the subjective side are signs of the corpus deli of the crime. In criminal law, special attention is usually paid to the problem of the subject of the crime [1]. This problem remains relevant today..

The subject is an inevitable sign of any crime. Criminal activity cannot be carried out without a subject. The characteristics of the subject are confirmed in articles 17-19 of the second part of the General Part of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan entitled "Persons to be held accountable" - this is a sane natural person who has reached the age of criminal responsibility.

The concept of a natural person is not defined in the criminal law, but there is no need for it, because the widely used meaning of this phrase means a person, regardless of the nationality of the country and other characteristics. This concept is defined in the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan: "natural persons mean citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan, citizens of other countries, as well as stateless persons".

Unlike foreign countries (Great Britain, Germany, China, USA, France, etc.), including countries belonging to the Romano-Germanic legal system, the criminal law of the Republic of Uzbekistan does not include criminal liability of legal entities. In some legal literature, one can come across opinions on the possibility of determining such legal responsibility [2, pp. 7-25; 3, p. 14]. Currently, in our Republic, legal entities can only be held administratively or civilly liable.

Article 18 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan defines the important features of the subject - the concepts of sanity and insanity. A person who, at the time of committing a crime, realized the socially dangerous nature of his act and was able to control his actions, is considered sane. A person who was mentally deranged at the time of committing a socially dangerous act, i.e. a person who could not understand the importance of his actions or could not control his actions due to chronic mental illness, temporary mental disorder, mental retardation or other mental illness, shall not be held liable. Coercive medical measures may be applied to a person who commits a socially dangerous act and is found mentally deficient by the court.

As a general rule, sane persons who have reached the age of sixteen at the time of committing the crime shall be held criminally liable for the crime committed. When determining the age of criminal responsibility, the legislator relies on information from medicine, psychology and other sciences.

It is self-evident that the person facing criminal responsibility must understand the nature and significance of the actions he is committing, as well as be able to control them. This ability appears in a person when he reaches a certain age, after he has accumulated enough knowledge and formed his basic views on how to behave in public. According to these regulations, a person who has reached the age of 16 can be the subject of the crime of human trafficking.

The second necessary sign of a criminal subject is sanity, that is, the ability of a person to understand the true nature and social significance of his behavior and control it. A person cannot be held criminally liable if there are circumstances provided for in Article 18 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

These internationally recognized criminals are often referred to as "traffickers".

But we oppose the use of this definition in relation to the subjects of the crime of attraction of people for the purpose of exploitation, because there is a difference in the goals of the criminals who commit the crime of human trafficking and the people who exploit people. In human trafficking, if the criminal directly attracts a person for future sale, when attracting people for the purpose of exploitation, it is not always intended to sell them, but they exploit them together with themselves or their criminal partners and receive profit, therefore, there may not be signs of human trafficking.

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Combating Human Trafficking" defines the concept of "trafficking person", according to it, a person engaged in

human trafficking is a natural or legal person who independently or as part of a group of persons commits any act related to human trafficking, as well as an official who, by his actions, facilitates human trafficking, as well as an official who does not prevent or fight human trafficking even though he is required to prevent and fight it according to his official authority.

M.H. Rustamboev, Q.R. Abdurasulova, S.S. Niyozova and N.B. Gurbanov expressed their opinion on this concept and explained that this concept is not correct and the phrase "a person engaged in human trafficking" is "a person who has carried out human trafficking" [4, p. 46] suggested to replace it with the phrase "person". It should be noted.

It should be noted that the anti-trafficking laws of many foreign countries approach this concept in the same way as the current law. In particular, Article 1 of the Law of the Kyrgyz Republic "On Prevention and Combating Human Trafficking" [5, p. 230], Article 1 of the Law of the Republic of Tajikistan "On Combating Human Trafficking" [6, p. 251.] and in Article 1 of the Law of the Republic of Turkmenistan "On Combating Human Trafficking" [7, p. 264] the concept of "trafficking person" is used.

In the orthographic dictionary of the Uzbek language, it is noted that the word "engagement" means "to be busy with some work, to carry out work" [p. 8, 10]. In other words, to be engaged is to engage in a certain type of activity regularly and legally. From this point of view, it is difficult to say that the definition given in the law is perfect.

At the same time, it follows from the wording of the law that perpetrators and assistants in the commission of human trafficking can be the subject of a crime, while the actions of organizers and agents are not considered human trafficking. H.Sh.Khamraeva uses the term "witnesses" [9, p. 30] in relation to crime participants in her research. But we cannot agree with this term either, because in civil law, a person participating in sales contracts is a "broker". In criminal law, there are concepts of participation such as witness, assistant, executor.

In our opinion, it is appropriate to change the name and definition of the concept of "person engaged in human trafficking" in the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Combating Human Trafficking", and to state this definition in the following version:

the subject of the crime of human trafficking -

1) a sane natural person over the age of 16 who has committed any act or omission related to human trafficking directly alone or together with other

persons (as a group of persons) (including a natural person acting on behalf of a legal entity);

2) participants in human trafficking - an organizer who led the preparation of human trafficking or the commission of a crime, a witness interested in its commission, who assisted in its commission with their advice, instructions, providing tools or removing obstacles, the criminal, the weapon of crime, traces and an accomplice who has made a prior promise to conceal means or things obtained through criminal means, to receive and transfer such things;

3) an official who does not prevent or fight against human trafficking, although he is obliged to prevent and fight against it according to his official authority.

In criminal law, there is also a special subject of the crime, which directly expresses the special nature of the crime. As noted by M.Usmonaliev and P.Bakunov, "a special subject of a crime, expressing a special nature of the crime, having additional special characteristics, in addition to the general characteristics of the subject of the crime (sanity, reaching the legal age) provided for in the disposition of the criminal law norm. it is said to the person" [10, p. 243]. According to V. M. Lebedev, "the presence of a special subject in the crime is a sign that distinguishes the crime committed by the criminal from other subjects" [11, p. 38].

Article 135 of the Criminal Code applies the special subject rule for cases of repeated, dangerous recidivist, extremely dangerous recidivist, organized group or use of official position.

In particular, paragraph "j" of the second part of Article 135 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan refers to a special subject - a person who commits the crime of human trafficking using his official position. In this case, "official position" is not associated with the position of an official, but means any service status in a state or non-state institution, enterprise or organization, and if the rights and opportunities associated with this status are used to commit the actions specified in Article 135 of the Criminal Code, the appropriate criminal liability is provided.

References:

1. Pavlo V.G. Sub'ekt prestupleniya. – SPb., 2000 yil.
2. Nikiforov A.S. Yuridicheskoe litso kak sub'ekt prestupleniya va ugovnoy otvetnosti. – M., 2002. – S. 7–25.
3. Ovcharova E.V. Materialno-pravovye problemy administrativnoy otvetstvennosti yuridicheskix lits // Gosudarstvo i pravo. 1998. №7. – S. 14.

4. Rustamboev M.H., Abdurasulova Q.R., Niyozova S.S., Qurbonov N.B. Odam savdosiga qarshi kurash muammolari: Monografiya. / Mas'ul muxarrir: O.G.Zokirova. – Toshkent: TDUI, 2011. – B. 46.
5. Mamlakatning “Odam savdosining oldini olish va unga qarshi kurashish”gi 2005 yil 17 martdagi qonuni 1-moddasi. // Odam savdosiga qarshi kurashda milliy va qonuniy qoidalari. / Tuzuvchilar L.Isxoqova, K.mroeva. – Toshkent: Yutist-media markazi, 2010. – B. 230.
6. Tojikiston Davlatning “Odam savdosiga qarshi kurash to‘g‘rsida”gi 2004 yil 15 iyuldagi qonuni 1-moddasi. // Odam savdosiga qarshi kurashda milliy va qonuniy qoidalari. / Tuzuvchilar L.Isxoqova, K.mroeva. – Toshkent: Yutist-media markazi, 2010. – B. 251.
7. orqa tomonning “Odam savdosiga qarshi kurash tog‘r”gi 207 yil 14 dekabrda qonunida 1-moddasi. // Odam savdosiga qarshi kurashda milliy va qonuniy qoidalari. / Tuzuvchilar L.Isxoqova, K.mroeva. – Toshkent: Yutist-media markazi, 2010. – B. 264.
8. O‘zbek tilining izhli lug‘ati: 80000 dan ortiq so‘z va so‘z birikmasi. T.5. Shukrona-H. – Toshkent: “O‘zbekiston milliy entsiklopediyasi” Davlat ilmiy nashriyoti, 2008. – B. 10.
9. Xamraeva Sh.H. Ayollar traffigi (pullashni barataf etishning o‘zgartirish-xuquqiy muammolari). Yurid.fan.nom. olish uchun diss. avtoref. – Toshkent: TDUI, 2004. – B. 30.
10. Usmonalev M., Bakunov P.B. Jinoyat haqida. (Umumiy qism): Darslik. – Toshkent: Nasaf, 2010. – B. 243.
11. Kommentariy ko Ugolovnomu kodeksi Rossiya Federasiyasi. / Pod.red. Lebedeva V.M.- Moskva: Norma, 2003. – S. 38

